

D2.7 Technical Documentation of R3: Planning Module

WP2 Development of Computed Assisted Waste Management Systems

FDEUSTO
Report
Public

Reviewers: MOBA, SGI

Version	Date	Description of main changes	Author
0.5	15/11/2017	Contribution to Softline	Softline
1.0	30/11/2017	First Draft	FDEUSTO
1.1	4/11/2017	Review from MOBA	MOBA
1.2	11/12/2017	Review from SGI	SGI
2.0	15/12/2017	Second Draft	FDEUSTO

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List of Abbreviations and Acronyms

Acronym	Definition
CEP	Complex Event Processing
D2D	Door to door
EA	Evolutionary Algorithms
EWC	European Waste Catalogue
GE.R.A	Gestione delle Risorse e delle Attività
GSS	GeoSmartSim
GUI	Graphic User Interface
JSON	JavaScript Object Notation
KPI	Key Performance indicator
MAS	Multi-Agent System
PAYT	Pay as you throw
RFID	Radio-frequency identification

Glossary

Concept	Definition
GeoSmartSim	Smart Simulation Engine
GE.R.A	It is the Italian acronym for “Gestione delle Risorse e delle Attività”, which means “Resources and Activities Management”

1. Introduction

In this deliverable we provide the technical description of the R3: Planning Module. This module will consist of several components that will help waste managers improve the planning of the system. Section 2 will provide a broad description of all the components of R2 and its relations with the rest of solutions developed in the Waste4Think. Section 3 covers the GE.R.A. system, a Mid Term Planning module. Section 4 will cover the Long-Term Planning model. Section 5 will be devoted to the Green Procurement tool and, Section 6 will present the Zero Waste Ecosystem/Events Planner, Section 7 will present the Social Actions Module, and finally, Section 8 will focus on the Invoicing Module.

Please note that this document only provides the technical description of R3: Planning Module, the status of the development can be read in **the Monitoring Action Reports (D1.4 to D1.7)**.

2. Relation with the rest of components

The Planning Module (R3) is the software module of Waste4Think devoted to help urban planners and waste collection companies in the planning of the Waste Management System. It consists of four different tools:

- **Planning Tools:** these are the central tools of the module. It is composed of two sub-tools:
 - **Mid Term Planning Tool:** This tool will help with the mid-term planning of the human resources, vehicles, equipment resources, and collection routes (weeks to month ahead). Sections 3 will present the details of this tool.
 - **Long Term Planning Tool:** This tool will help with the long-term planning of the waste management system (years ahead). Sections 4 contains the details of this tool.
- **Green Procurement:** this tool will help in the writing and evaluation of green procurements. Section 5 is devoted to this tool.
- **Zero Waste Ecosystem planner:** this tool allows the planning and monitoring of Zero Waste events and Ecosystems. Section 6 contains the details of this tool.
- **Social Action planner:** this tool allows to plan and monitor a Social Action Strategy. Section 7 covers the details of this tool.
- **Invoicing module:** this tool will allow to holistically assess the impact that the introduction of innovative economic instruments (PAYT) will have. Section 8 details this tool. Please note that this tool only covers the simulation of the impact of introducing new economic instruments and not the management of them (invoice generation, management, etc.). This will be covered in detail in Deliverable D5.1.

Figure 1 shows the relations of these components (in blue) with the rest of eco-solutions of Waste4Think. As can be seen, R1 and R3 are highly interconnected:

- first, the information that the previous tools need comes from the different components of R1 (the Context Broker and the Persistence layer),
- moreover, the models used to perform several of the operations will be deployed in the Complex Event Processing (CEP) engine, and
- finally, some of the tools of R3 will be accessible through the W4T-core component of R1, specifically, the Green Procurement, the Zero Waste Ecosystem/Event planner and the Invoice Module. Finally, the visualization of the results will use the Dashboard (R1).

Another important aspect to mention is the integration between the Serious Games and the Long-Term Planner as it will be used in the Planning Game as a source of information.

Figure 1. Relation of the architecture of R3 with the overall architecture of Waste4Think.

The main use cases for these tools are A1 and A16, but are also related to C5, C13 and S10 (see Deliverable D1.1). The list of functional requirements fulfilled by the components of R3 are as shown in Table 1.

Table 1. Functional Requirement fulfilled by the components of R3.

ID	FR	Mid-Term	Long-Term Planning	Green Procurement	Zero-Waste Ecosystems/	Social Actions planner	Invoicing
R3_FR1	To support the long-term planning	X	X				
R3_FR1.1	Provide visual tools to create predictive and explicative models		X				
R3_FR1.2	Provide visuals tools to help in the creation of baselines and what-if scenarios		X				
R3_FR1.2.1	Allow to modify in what-if scenarios the projected population and their spatial distribution		X				
R3_FR1.2.2	Allow to modify in what-if scenarios the waste type and quantity		X				
R3_FR1.2.3	Allow to modify in what-if scenarios the introduction of new treatment plants		X				
R3_FR1.2.4	Allow to modify in what-if scenarios the introduction of new collection systems	X	X				
R3_FR1.2.5	Allow to modify in what-if scenarios the mean for waste collection (electric truck, etc.)		X				
R3_FR1.2.6	Allow to modify in what-if scenarios the localization of the collection spots	X	X				
R3_FR1.2.7	Allow to modify in what-if scenarios the prevention campaigns		X		X		
R3_FR1.2.8	Allow to introduce and / or modify the economic instruments (tariff, PAYT, etc.)	X	X				X
R3_FR1.3	Perform long term simulations of the waste management system	X	X				
R3_FR1.3.1	Simulate the combination of collection system plus treatment plans		X				

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R3_FR1.3.2	Simulate the localization and size of the collection points and treatment plans	X	X				
R3_FR1.3.3	Simulate combinations of prevention campaigns					X	
R3_FR1.3.4	Take into consideration multiple criteria (economical, environmental and social impacts)		X				
R3_FR1.3.5	Simulate different transport means for waste collection		X				
R3_FR1.3.6	Simulate the effect of different combination of economic instruments						X
R3_FR1.4	Allow the optimization of the waste collection for special events				X		
R3_FR1.5	Help in the creation of green procurements			X			
R3_FR1.5.1	To identify criteria for the tendering			X			
R3_FR1.5.2	To evaluate the applicants of the tender			X			

3. Mid-term Planning G.E.R.A

G.E.R.A is the Italian acronym for “Gestione delle Risorse e delle Attività”, which means “Resources and Activities Management”. Softline has implemented it during this project. GE.R.A is based on an optimization algorithm which gives search keys and task management processing through cost minimization and optimization in the use of staff. In fact, it can determine the human resources, vehicles and activities necessary to do a specific activity and considering, as inputs, all economic / administrative data relating to people and vehicles.

Activities can be programmed by analysing costs at each stage, from the estimate budget to real final budget, planning services through accurate matching between human and vehicle resources. Innovation, therefore, consists on the development of new parameters which the system considers to better make the activity planning. Another important task is that the system allows to manage the work plan on mobile devices, such as smartphones and / or tablets, to be used by the operators during their works on site allowing them to efficiently report the worked hours and fuel consumption. Finally, the system is integrated with call handling services enabling communication between users and the service provider in real time.

Figure 2. Components of G.E.R.A

The following sections describe in detail the components shown in Figure 2.

3.1. Databases

Data Model which describes the requested information of the system is detailed. Figure 3 represents the tables with information about operators. All the data about operators are recorded in the database to operate the optimization, monitoring and financial reports of the services. More in detail, the following aspects are recorded:

- Financial reports
- Issues
- Deadlines
- Driving licenses
- Tasks: it indicates at which activities the operator can work; a weight is given to each activity in order to point out which activity the operator should preferably do.

- Clocking in/out
- Agreements costs
- Agreements

Figure 3. Scheme of the tables which describe information about operators

Figure 4 shows the main tables describing information about vehicles and equipment.

The information regards:

- Maintenances
- Deadlines
- Costs
- Routes/RFID readings

Figure 4. Tables of information about vehicles and equipment's

Figure 5 shows the scheme of the main table containing information about Orders. A group of services composes an order. The service represents the set of activities to be done in an area of the Municipality.

The table of service has the following details:

- Frequency of the specific activity
- The zone in which the service is planned for
- The type of waste (EWC)
 - The category of the service:
 1. door to door collection of a specific waste type (paper, glass, organic waste, undifferentiated waste, etc)

2. bin collection of a specific waste type (paper, glass, organic waste, undifferentiated waste, etc)
3. Household waste centre.

Activities are related to the service. An activity is represented by providing the operator's task requested, the possible category of the means provided, any equipment needed to the activity and the time slot in which the activity must be carried out.

Figure 5. Tables of data which define the Order structure

Figure 6 shows a table diagram that describes the information about the service and activity time-table. The time-table is the result of the assignment of vehicles, equipment and people to the services previously defined

Figure 6. Table diagram that describes the information about services and activities time-table.

3.2 Optimization module

The daily/weekly activity planning for make a waste collection is the output of the optimization process. The optimized collection will consist on a set of recommendations about:

- type of collection (door to door for each type of waste, bin collection, ecologic island)
- zones (this information gives to the system the frequency for the waste collection type and the modality to be used for that zone)
- resources (how many and which operators, how many and which vehicles or equipment, how many and which equipment for that kind of service at a specific frequency)

This output can be compared to the real management of the waste collection for better matches the next planning: real fuel consumption, different human resource chosen by the responsible of the waste collection because the availabilities of those planned in the software were changed, etc. Finally, the software restores all these real data to create a history of the management choices and better give the next planning.

The optimization modules will be developed by the staff of the Softline itself.

3.2.1 Optimization of service planning

The module is designed to optimize:

- ✓ personnel,
- ✓ collection vehicles
- ✓ necessary equipment for every service

to each activity with the aim of reducing company impact by optimizing personnel involvement and vehicles/equipment.

Employees are assigned for different activities by checking constraints such as:

- 1) The presence during the service period evaluating also the assigned weight which every operator has for a specify mansion.
- 2) Presence, no absence due to illness reported, holidays or other
- 3) Congruity (and validity) of the license with any necessary vehicle
- 4) check of the deadlines of the vehicle itself, etc.

The vehicles for the waste collection and the necessary equipment are used on the basis of availability in the planned period of activity.

3.2.2 Optimization of services based on the history accountability

The module analyses post-service data and tries to pinpoint margins of qualitative and quantitative improvements from a resource utilization point view.

The analysis considers:

- ✓ collected kilograms of waste per shift
- ✓ number of collections
- ✓ number of vehicle stops for collection
- ✓ km travelled
- ✓ time spent
- ✓ fuel consumption
- ✓ vehicle depreciation
- ✓ personnel costs
- ✓ consumption costs

- ✓ capacity of the trucks/vehicles
- ✓ filling of vehicle at the end of the service

Based on the data collected, various indicators are calculated to measure the cost of the service, for example:

- cost/hour
- cost/km
- percentage of vehicle use based on its operative availability,
- percentage of personnel use based on its operative availability
- volume collected / available medium volume
- etc.

Analyzing the various parameters and comparing them over a period of reference, the following parameters will be identified:

- the elements that can lead to reviewing their service planning,
- the frequency of collection and
- the use of means more coherent with the quantities to be collected

3.3 User interface

Figure 7 shows the G.E.R.A. command panel for the user-interface. It is possible to read from the left to the right the following commands/tools:

- 1) **Homepage**: when the user selects it, the tool will provide the main data required by the management – Agenda, Financial report, Deadlines, Messages;
- 2.1) **Operators data**: when the user selects it, the tool will provide the Operator panel (Figure 9);
- 2.2) **Attendance management**: the tool will provide where the operators can manage their incoming and exit
- 3.1) **Vehicles/equipments**: when the user selects it, the tool will provide the vehicles/equipment panel (Figure 10).
- 3.2) Near the **Vehicle/Equipment** key, from up to down the first key provide the **maintenance management tool**, the second the **refueling** and the third the **analysis of vehicle costs**;
- 4.1) **Services/Order**: when the user selects it, the tool will provide the Order panel (Figure 11);
- 4.2) **Time-Tables**: when the user selects it, the tool will provide the time-tables panel (Figure 12);
- 5.1) **Providers**: it is possible to see a list of providers of the Company when the user selects it;
- 5.2) **Basic Tables**: when the user selects it, the tool will provide the main table of the G.E.R.A. system.

Figure 7. G.E.R.A command panel

As it is shown, the system considers the whole managements of a waste collection company. As this deliverable and in particular our task regards the mid-term planning, the main section will be described in the following text.

The access to the program requires an authentication, and each user may be granted different access to data or modification (Figure 8). Only enabled users can fill in the different sections. In FACT, on the left of the panel control, it is possible to find the type of policy that can be defined (bold text), while in the right window there are the list of components on which it is possible to apply the selected policy.

Along the bar above the mentioned windows there are six keys:

- The first two left keys indicate the “+” and “x”: they are useful to directly add and remove policies.
- The third key is the “locket” and indicate o set policy unable/able
- Then there is the “magnifying glass” key, which is used to set how policy should be shown or not.
- The “agenda” key is used to set how policy type should be only read
- The last key is used to set policy type as a custom action.

Figure 8. Policy definition for the access of the users

Specifically, the main masks that the operators will use are that for the Operator, the Equipment, the Order and the Timetable.

Each mask is composed mainly of three Sections, the name of the sections is generally the same for all masks:

- Section A is on the left of the window and represents a tree view of the folders that the user must select to open the grids at the right of the window to fill in the requested data.
- On the right of the window there are two grids indicate as Section B and C. Section B is above section C and contains the list of all Operators, Equipment, Order and Timetable (as the name of the masks indicate). When the user selects a folder from the tree view in Section A it is possible to see the detail to be filled in on the grid called Section C.
- Only the mask of the Timetable is represented with different grids because this mask is used principally to visualize the resource planning, which is the output of the whole system.

An explanation of the main mask visualized as graphic interface follow without specifically indicate each key involved on:

1) **Operators Graphic User Interface** (GUI) (Figure 9).

- ✓ At the left of the window, there is a tree view (**section A** in Figure 9Error! Reference source not found.): the main folders are three (a, b, c folders) and each one contains a list of details concerning the single operator. The c folder is not visible in this screenshot of the GUI. For better explain the Italian text of the GUI, a short list of the tree view follow:
 - a) **Folder a “Operators”**:
 - a.1) **Attendance**:
 - Attendance
 - Clocking in/out
 - Availability
 - Absences
 - Trips
 - a.2) **Agreement**:
 - Tasks
 - Contracts
 - Rebuke
 - Fines
 - Personal equipment
 - a.3) **Personal data**
 - contact numbers
 - Bank account
 - **Etc.**
 - a.4) **Deadlines**
 - a.5) **Orders/Shift**: this folder is important as it connects the personal with the orders and activities
 - Orders
 - Services
 - Shifts
 - Financial Report
 - b) **Folder b “Tables”**:
 - b.1) concessions
 - b.2) Protected categories
 - b.3) Licenses
 - b.4) Training courses
 - b.5) Tasks
 - b.6) etc
 - c) **Folder c “tables/equipment”**:
 - c.1) type of equipment
 - c.2) etc

At the right of the window, there are two grids (sections B and C in Figure 9):

- ✓ The top one, **section B operators**, contains the details for each operator.
- ✓ The bottom one, **section C**, indicates the **tasks** in this case because the homonym folder is being selected from the section A - tree view. It is a grid to be filled in and where the main inputs required for the optimization are:

- the B.1) **coefficient of difficulty** that indicate how much a specific task is laborious, in fact the optimization system tries to not overload an operator which tasks have a heavy weight compared to other tasks.
- the B.2) **weight** relative to the operator: if for the same task there are more operators, the system selects those that have more weight for that job.

Figure 9: "Operator" GUI

2) Figure 10 shows the **vehicles/equipment interface**.

✓ At the left of the window, there is a tree view (**section A of the Error! Reference source not found.**): the main folders are three (a, b, c folders).

a) **Folder a "vehicles and trucks"** contains a detailed list to be filled in about the vehicles, such as:

- deadlines
- vehicles stoppage
- depreciation
- costs
- maintenance
- fuel cards
- surveys km
- etc...

a.1) **Orders/Shift:** this folder is important as it connects the vehicles with the orders and activitier

- Orders
- Activities
- Shift

- b) Folder b “Equipment” contains folders to be filled in on the machines, tools and materials of the site.
- c) Folder c “Tables” :
 - Permissions
 - Fuels
 - Vehicle categories
 - Etc
- ✓ Section B is a grid with the detail of the Equipment.
- ✓ Section C is a grid that represents the selected choice that the user has done from the Section A, the tree view. Here it is the Section C.1 where it is important to indicate the amount of consumed fuel for each vehicle.

Figure 10. “Vehicles/equipments” GUI

- 3) Figure 11 shows the order/services GUI.
- ✓ There is a tree view at the left of the window (section A of Figure 11): the main folders are two (a, b folders).
 - a) Folder a “Sectors” :
 - Categories of Services
 - Services codes
 - b) Folder a “Orders” :
 - Services
 - operator transfers
 - clients
 - operators
 - vehicles
 - equipment
 - construction sites
- ✓ Section B is a grid with the detail of the Orders.
- ✓ Section C should be fill in indicating the Sector of the Company, the service category and the Service Code

- ✓ **Section D** should be fill in indicating the specific activities of the service. In this grid is important to fill in the **Difficulty coefficient (D.1)** that will be use from the optimizer.

The screenshot displays the GeRA - Commesse software interface. The main window is titled 'Commesse' and contains a table of contracts. The table has columns for 'Id Commessa Gera', 'Desc Commessa Gera', 'Settore', 'Data Inizio Commessa', 'Data Fine Commessa', 'Id Responsabile Commessa', 'Valore Contrattuale', 'Codice Commessa', 'Commessa Con Trasferte', and 'Cup'. The table lists various contracts, including 'URB - SAN VITO DEI NORMANNI', 'URB - ENEL PUGLIA E BASILICATA 2014', and 'URB - ENEL CALABRIA 2015'.

Below the main table, there is a section for 'Servizi' (Services) with a tree view on the left and a detailed view on the right. The tree view shows a hierarchy of services, including 'URB - IGIENE E COMPLEMENT' and 'URB - RACCOLTA RSU'. The detailed view shows a table with columns for 'Attività', 'Desc Attività', 'Desc Mansione', 'Desc Categoria Automezzo', and 'Coefficiente Difficoltà'. A specific activity is highlighted, showing 'DERATTIZZAZIONE' with a 'Coefficiente Difficoltà' of 5. This coefficient is labeled 'D.1' in the image.

Labels A, B, C, and D are placed on the screenshot to indicate specific sections: A points to the left sidebar, B points to the main table, C points to the service tree view, and D points to the detailed activity table.

Figure 11. "Order" GUI

4) Figure 12 shows the **time-table GUI**.

This mask is quite different from the above described. In fact, here it is possible to visualize different grids and there is not a tree view. Briefly the main section is here reported:

- ✓ Section A is a table in which the rows are the days of the calendar, the columns are the services, the cells are marked by the operators and the vehicles assigned to the activities related to the service.
- ✓ Section B shows all the operators, vehicles and equipment available in the day. You can change the composition of a service moving by a drag and drop the resources from one table to another.
- ✓ Section D shows the calendar
- ✓ Section E is used to filter the Municipalities or Zones of a specific Order that the user wants to visualize
- ✓ Section F is used to filter the services of the Municipality or Zone of a specific Order that the user is above selected.

Calendario Turni - 1308x876

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Calendario Turni Oggi Giornaliera Settimanale Mensile Azzera Calendario Scheduler Stampa Aggiorna Sistema Chiudi

Tabellone Servizi Tabellone Operatori Tabellone Automezzi Elenco Turnazioni Debug

Aggiorna Stampa SQL

A

Servizi	27/11/2017			28/11/2017			29/11/2017		
PAP ORGANICO SAN VITO DEI NORMANNI - URB SAN VITO CONTRADE EST	Orario	Nominativo	Targa	Orario	Nominativo	Targa	Orario	Nominativo	Targa
	12.00-18.00	VITA CATALDO	EM112PE						
PAP ORGANICO SAN VITO DEI NORMANNI - URB SAN VITO CONTRADE NORD	Orario	Nominativo	Targa	Orario	Nominativo	Targa	Orario	Nominativo	Targa
	12.00-18.00	VITA CATALDO	EM112PE						
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	12.00-18.00	VITA CATALDO	EM112PE						

B

Operatori	27/11/2017	28/11/2017	29/11/2017
Perez Angelo Bruno Pietro Prete Alfonso Dai Gianfranco Piccione Santo	Vita Cataldo Perez Angelo Bruno Pietro Prete Alfonso Dai Gianfranco	Vita Cataldo Perez Angelo Bruno Pietro Prete Alfonso Dai Gianfranco	Vita Cataldo Perez Angelo Bruno Pietro Prete Alfonso Dai Gianfranco
Automezzi	DG9098F IVECO 120E15 DG9098F IVECO 120E15 DW950TR IVECO 120E18 KR DW950TR IVECO 120E18 KR DW950TR IVECO 120E18 KR	DG9098F IVECO 120E15 DG9098F IVECO 120E15 DW950TR IVECO 120E18 KR DW950TR IVECO 120E18 KR DW950TR IVECO 120E18 KR	DG9098F IVECO 120E15 DG9098F IVECO 120E15 DW950TR IVECO 120E18 KR DW950TR IVECO 120E18 KR DW950TR IVECO 120E18 KR
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D

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17	18	19	20	21	22
23	24	25	26	27	28
29	30	1	2	3	4
5	6	7	8	9	10

E

Filtro Comuni/Zone

- Comesse
- URB - SAN VITO DEI NORMANNI
- BON - ENEL PUGLIA E BASILICATA
- MICRORACCOLTA
- MAC - VESTAS

F

Seleziona

- Servizi
- ALTRE OPERE
- BONIFICA AMIANTO E/R
- BONIFICAZIONE SITI CONTAMINATI
- DEMOLIZIONI CIVILI / ID
- IMPIANTI TECNOLOGICI
- INDAGINI E ANALISI AM
- OPERE EDILI
- RACCOLTA RSU E ASSINAPAZIONE
- RACCOLTA RIFIUTI SPE
- TRASPORTI DA CENTRI
- TRASPORTI DA IMPIANTI

GeRA - Comesse Calendario Turni GeRA - Automezzi/Attrezzature GeRA - Operatori

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Figure 12. Time-Tables GUI

4. Long-Term Planning

One of the main challenges of simulating human societies is taking into consideration all the complex decisions and events that influence everyday decisions. All individuals want to achieve a set of goals for which it is necessary to interact, compete and cooperate with others. It is this complex behaviour that needs to be tackled from a different point of modelling taking into play physical, social, cultural and economic aspects of everyday relations.

GeoSmartSim (GSS) is a Geographical Simulations Engine [1] combining Geographic Information System's techniques with a Multi-Agent System [2] to reproduce dynamic urban environments. Multi-agent environments allow a bottom-up modelling, where all agents collaborate and compete against each other while interacting with the environment. In this way, a model is defined and run through a simulation, whose results vary depending on both the characteristics of the agents and their decision processes. The advantage of this approach is the feasibility to parameterize different scenarios and evaluate how the different individuals behaviour and interactions are affected each time.

The platform will receive a scenario built with the Scenario Definition Tool containing information about the features and entities that need to take place in the simulation. Please note that a scenario will contain both data from the Current State and Other Information (that could be historical, future plans or from a what-if scenario). It will then process the scenario by running all the agents in a Monte-Carlo simulation and finally bulk the results into the Context Broker hosting simulations database. Figure 13 graphically describes this flow of information.

Figure 13. Components of the Long-Term Planning tool.

4.1. Scenario Definition tool

The Scenario Definition tool will be accessible through the side menu of the W4T-Core. Please note that W4T-Core has been described in Deliverable D2.1 (Figure 14).

When the user accesses the Scenario Definition tool, they will be presented with **a list of the simulations that are currently active** (Figure 15). At first glance, the user will be able to identify the important details about the simulations, such as the name, a short description of its purpose, a map stating its geographical boundaries, and its status (running, finished, error, etc). The user can either **create** a new scenario or click on any of the existing simulations to **launch a detailed view of the specific configuration**.

Figure 14. Access to Scenario Definition Tool through the side menu of W4T-Core

Figure 15. Main view of the Scenario Definition Tool

4.1.1. Creation of a new simulation scenario

When the user selects the option to **Create a new simulation**, they will be presented with a guide that will help them configure the new simulation scenario (Figure 16) through the definition of the following inputs.

- **Basic details.** Define attributes such as the name, the description, and the geographical (location) and temporal (start and end date) boundaries of the simulation.
- **Simulation Model:** Choose from a list of available optimization models, the one that will be tested on the simulation. Each model will be parametrized according to its specific operation through a JSON configuration file that can be uploaded by the user.
- **Data source:** All simulation scenarios need data on which to perform the simulation. For example, this data may include the definition of the amount and type of people in a certain geographical zone, the location of the waste containers, the routes of the waste trucks, etc. The user can either select to use t a) real data retrieved from the current status and measurements of the pilots, b) simulated data from a previously configured scenario, or c) create new scenario with new set of data (Figure 17).

Figure 16. Create new simulation scenario within the Scenario Definition Tool

Figure 17. Create new scenario resources

4.1.2. Editing an existing simulation scenario

When the user selects *an existing simulation scenario*, they will be presented with a view, similar to the one used during its creation. In this case, all the configuration data will be already loaded. From this view the user can select to either stop the simulation and rerun it with newly configured parameters, or cancel the simulation.

Figure 18. Edit View of the Long-Term Planning Tool

The scenarios will follow the schema described in Deliverable D2.1, which defines the types of entities to be used and monitored in the Waste4Think modules. The entities to use in what-if scenarios are:

- **Citizens:** People, shops or industries hosted in a certain municipality or geographic area will be modelled as *WasteEntities* from the schema defined in Deliverable D2.1, Section 4.2.3. It will be possible to, on the one hand, load the real-world data from the Context Broker to recreate a real-world scenario or, on the other hand, manually or through a shapefile format file to create fictional citizens, shops or industries for what-if scenario testing:
 - *WasteEntity*: Each instance where waste is created, transformed or consumed, belonging to a *WasteEntityType* and containing the location of the entity together with the specific features that describe the recycling behaviour, awareness and generation pattern.
 - *WasteEntityType*: Description of a group of citizens, shops, industries etc. that will take part in the waste flow, generating, transforming or consuming waste. For each entity type, the usual waste inputs and outputs will be enumerated.
- **Recycling behaviours:** Model for characterizing the way each citizen generates and throws its waste. One of the main points for the simulations is emulating in a reliable way, the behaviour citizens have when generating wastes and choosing how and where to throw them. The recycling behaviour model will take into consideration all socio-economic aspects of each citizen together with its recycling awareness and create the actions each individual will perform. These statistical models are usually built using Regression models or Generalized linear models that are trained from raw data [3]. Our model will combine state of the art models, raw data and surveys carried out to the project pilots.

- **Deposit points:** Traditional containers or newly introduced door2door systems are modelled through the DepositPoint entities. These are composed of the model defined in Deliverable D2.1, Sections 4.2.1 and 4.2.2. Just the same as with citizens, DepositPoint data will be extracted both from the Context Broker for real world scenarios or from manual and SHP files for what-if fiction scenarios. The entities to load are as follows:
 - *Waste*: The material discarded by citizens or business' after primary use. A waste can be almost any material which is worthless for the user. Nevertheless, it can be useful for another agent as input.
 - *WasteCategory*: A higher level category that describes some features all of its child wastes share such as origin, material, fabrication process, etc.
 - *SortingType*: Grouping of wastes that are collected together in a country or service area. Sorting types usually vary according to legislation, collecting company or technical requirements. Traditional sorting types are usually light packaging, glass bottles, paper and cardboard, organic waste and refuse.
 - *DepositPoint*: Place where waste is deposited for its collection. It covers from traditional containers to less usual methods such as a personal plastic bag (in door2door systems), pneumatic waste dumpsters, fixed collection centers, mobile collection centers, etc.
 - *DepositPointType*: Container, bag, dumpster, etc. models with their features that are common to all DepositPoints from this type such as waste it contains, capacity, color, height, width, price, etc.
 - *DepositPointIsle*: A group of DepositPoints that belong together in a geographic area. This can be useful for calculations at DepositPointIsle level where there are more than one DepositPoint in a place and users tend to use them indifferently resulting in irregular measurements.
- **Waste Collection Systems:** Waste collection systems will be built using the model from Deliverable D2.1, Sections 4.2.1 and 4.2.4. Scenario data will be gathered from the real-world scenario hosted in the Context Broker or from manually and SHP files created data. The six main entities involved in waste management systems are:
 - *Waste*: The material discarded by citizens or business' after primary use. A waste can be almost any material which is worthless for the user. Nevertheless, it can be useful for another agent as input.
 - *WasteCategory*: A higher level category that describes some features all of its child wastes share such as origin, material, fabrication process, etc.
 - *SortingType*: Grouping of wastes that are collected together in a country or service area. Sorting types usually vary according to legislation, collecting company or technical requirements. Traditional sorting types are usually light packaging, glass bottles, paper and cardboard, organic waste and refuse.
 - *CollectionRoute*: A particular transport route with all properties which are common to multiple itinerary instances belonging to such model. A route is a way to identify a journey that is regularly made by a given transport in an agency.
 - *Itinerary*: A scheduled itinerary for a certain date and vehicle. It contains a list of ordered *ItinerarySegments* the vehicle should follow together with the estimated arrival and departure time.
 - *ItinerarySegment*: ItinerarySegment contains the information of the pieces that build the entire itinerary with the departure and arrival entities and times.

- **Transport Networks:** Road, highways, footways and paths will be loaded from the volunteer geographic information OpenStreetMap [CITA]. OpenStreetMap is a free, editable map of the whole world that is being built by volunteers containing a full detailed roadmap which is constantly updated by volunteers. Map elements use a key-value definition schema for describing each feature and its attributes. The key `highway=*` is the main key used for identifying any kind of road, street or path. The value of the key helps indicate the importance of the highway within the road network as a whole [5].

OpenStreetMap's data schema will automatically be downloaded and used for transport network modelling inside GSS. For every simulation, all the roads, highways and footways will be downloaded and connected in a transport network graph that is going to be used.

4.2. GeoSmartSim Simulation Engine

All GSS simulations are structured in three main pillars: agents, environment and skills. The next sections explain in detail every one of the pillars:

4.2.1. Agents

All the entities interfering in a scenario are modelled as agents. Each of these, is a piece of semi-autonomous software acting to carry out a task that satisfy its needs. This therefore, allows a finer parametrization of each individual in a more truthful way.

All agents have some basic properties and methods that identify them both geographically and logically:

- **Id:** Identification of the agent.
- **Type:** Class type of the agent.
- **Geometry:** Geographical representation and location of the agent.
- **Skills:** A set of skills for the agent to be able to perform operations.
- **Behaviour:** An active loop that will be executed constantly for the agent to select which operation to perform next and reach its goal.
- **Meta properties:** Extendable property system to add additional properties.

According to the complexity of these attributes agents are categorised in two different groups whether they have their own active behaviour, or they just react to stimuli:

4.2.1.1. Intelligent agents

Autonomous Agents constitute the traditional agents in a Multi-Agent System (MAS). They are scheduled to follow a certain behaviour and are active elements that start the actions. Their execution loop will be implemented with all the active process they follow to achieve their goals.

- **Citizens:** active agents in the simulations, citizens will be located and parametrized in the environment according to the data provided from the scenario editor tool. Each citizen will have a set of preferences that will characterize their recycling awareness, amount of waste they generate and maximum walking distance they are willing to travel to the container. Everyday agents will generate waste according to generation patterns stored and will try to throw it at the nearest container they have. Depending on the available deposit points, collection days and recycling awareness, citizens will make good or bad use of them.
- **Vehicle Drivers:** active agents that drive the collection vehicles. Vehicle drivers will have the *Skill* to schedule the itinerary for their assigned deposit points and reproduce the itinerary emptying or collecting the points and filling the vehicle. Altering the schedules will change the environmental, social and economic impacts together with how the citizens will use the deposit points.

4.2.1.2. Passive agents

Passive agents are those entities who, although having some logic inside, just react to the actions of other Entities. Namely, they provide or receive information from agents and other passive entities. Their behaviour loop must be empty and other agents will access and alter this agent's properties.

- **Transport Network:** roads, highways, footways and paths for the study area that will compound the environment in which the agents will live. Transport network will be downloaded from the volunteer geographic information OpenStreetMap creating a routing graph with the roads and highways for vehicles and footways and steps citizens can use for travelling.
- **Deposit Points:** representing traditional containers or Door2Door deposit points hosting one single sorting type. Each deposit point has its own capacity, filling level and location. These passive agents will just react to the citizens waste throwing by increasing their filling level and to the vehicles by emptying their filling levels.
- **Waste Treatment plants:** places where a certain waste is recycled. These agents will transform the received waste into resources (secondary RAW materials or energy) or just stored them (landfills).
- **Vehicles:** combustion or electric vehicles in charge of performing the collection itinerary. This passive agent will follow the orders of the driver and will emit emissions to the atmosphere together with fuel (if motorized) or energy (if electric) consumption.

4.2.2. Agent Environment

Agent Environments provide the virtual world where agents inhabit and the information and rules for them to act. Within MAS technologies, the Agent Environment concept has been recognised as an independent and living element which is essential to model dynamic real-world problems. Real Environments are inherently dynamic, that is, change beyond the agent's control and therefore this dynamism must be modelled explicitly as part of the simulated Environment by implementing processes that can change its own state.

- **Physical environment:** This layer of the environment is the one that models the geographical aspects of the entities that coexist in it. Deploys a Geographic Information System managing and limiting the movements agents can perform in the environment.
- **Time environment:** Section for time managing in the virtual world of the agents. They will be synchronized and scheduled according to the time the environment they live in.
- **Climate environment:** Atmospheric layers regarding temperature, humidity, sun irradiation and other measures that represent the weather situation of the environment.
- **Social Environment:** GeoSmartSim enables a SIGNAL/SLOT mechanism agent to use to receive interactions from other entities. Agents can subscribe slots to signals that other entities emit, resulting their slot being invoked when the emitter sends some information.
- **Network Environment:** For network modelling purposes (transport, water, power, etc.), two special classes GSSGraphEdge and GSSGraphNode are provided for agents to inherit from them. All agents that implement any of these two classes will be elements of a graph contained in the Network Environment.
- **Execution environment:** The environment oversees managing each agent turn to behave. The execution environment ensures all agents receive their execution time according to their needs and action times.

4.2.3. Skills

Skills are the degree of competence a living entity has when carrying out a certain task. GeoSmartSim implements a large battery of skills that enable agents sensing the environment, memorizing, processing information, making decisions, etc. Both intelligent and passive agents can have a set of skills to interact with the environment and alter its properties:

- Intelligent Agent Skills:
 - *Generate waste skill:* Waste generation behaviour for each citizen, shop or industry.
 - *Search Deposit points skills:* Environment look up skill for finding a citizen's best deposit points.

- *Decide use of deposit points skill*: Each agent's thinking process of whether to correctly use the deposit points or not according to distances, volume of waste and awareness.
- **Passive Agent Skills**
 - *Contain waste skill*: Skill of accepting waste from active agents until it reaches its maximum capacity.
 - *Vehicle move skill*: Ability for a combustion or electric vehicle to move. The vehicle will consume some resources for this purpose and emit several impacts and gases to the atmosphere.
 - *Transform waste skill*: Process of transforming waste into others for treatment plants.

4.3. Optimization Module

This module will oversee the different optimizations that the Long-Term Planner module could perform. The next sections will introduce the main aspects of both the GeoSimulation and the algorithms used to complete the task.

4.3.1. Key Performance Indicators (KPI)

The KPIs that come into play in the simulations are extracted from the global KPI list of the project described in Deliverable D1.3. Table 2 contains the list and objectives of the KPIs for the Planning Module. These KPIs will be used for scenario improvement evaluation in each of the modules described below.

Table 2. List of KPIs selected for the optimization.

Objectives	KPIs
Reduction of the municipal waste generation	T1. Average reduction of municipal waste generation (kg/year)
To eliminate the primary waste deposited into landfills and to maximize waste reuse and recycling	T2. Increase of the average of urban waste sorted
	T3 Decrease of the average of waste sent to final disposal
	T3.1 Dry recyclables to primary destination (%)
	T3.2 Organic recyclables to primary destination (%)
To improve the integral waste management service	T.3.3 Residual waste to primary destination (%)
	E.1.1 net GHG emissions (kg CO ₂ / kg of waste) collection & treatment
	C.1.2 Treatment canon (€/ton)
	C.1.3.1 Collection and Transport cost (€)
	C1.3.2 Final management cost (€)
	C1.3.3 Other common costs (€)
	C1.1 Budget applied to awareness and prevention campaigns (€)
S.2.1 Number of workers (n)	

4.3.2. Waste generation patterns optimization

This module will reproduce and simulate the citizens waste generation and how different social actions and incentives influence in their recycling awareness. To this end, this module will simulate the effect that different social actions will have on the citizens waste generation and recycling behaviour.

The main agents involved in the simulation will be:

- **Citizens:** the scenario will need the location of citizens together with their waste throwing characterization, recycling awareness and the maximum distance that a citizen is willing to walk to throw the waste separately.
- **Social Actions and Incentives:** List of strategies to be applied in the municipality to evaluate their effects in the citizens.

The goal is to be able to prioritize (or know) which social actions and incentives may have the most beneficial effects on the municipality and their side effects with respect to the KPIs defined in Table 2. The module will use evolutionary algorithms (EA) for evaluating if new scenarios provide a lower or greater waste generation and recycling rate. Each iteration, the EA will modify a population of scenarios changing the awareness and incentives of the citizens.

4.3.3. Waste sorting method and deposit points location module

This module will be in charge of assess the best sorting method for the scenario along with the optimization of the deposit points. First, the user should select the number of different fractions to collect. Then, the module will optimize the localization of the deposit points. Please note that pneumatic collection system could be assimilated to this one just changing the impact of the construction and operation of the infrastructure.

As it is known that recycling rates decrease with respect to the distance to the collection points, this module will evaluate the current situation of them to suggest a better location in order to improve recycling rates while keeping controlled the rest of impacts. To this end, the user will need to set some input scenario from which the agents and skills will be modelled as follows:

- **Citizens:** the scenario will need the location of citizens together with their waste throwing characterization, recycling awareness and the maximum distance that a particular citizen is willing to walk to throw the waste separately.
- **Deposit Points:** Models, collecting sorting types and initial location for deposit points. This will be used as baseline scenario from which to compare if simulated solutions improve the current scenario.
- **Transport Network:** for the citizens to find their nearest containers and make use of them will be loaded automatically to cover the study area.

The module will also use EA for evaluating if new scenarios provide a lower or greater recycling rate. Each iteration, the EA will modify a population of scenarios changing the location and properties of the deposit points. After each modification the algorithm will perform a simulation of the behaviour of the citizen in the new scenario and evaluate the result with respect of several of the KPIs defined in Deliverable D1.3. It will then start a new iteration using the population of improved scenarios as the base to be modified. Changing the location, sizes and collection days of the containers will then affect the decisions of the citizens and result in a better or worse separation rate. Finally, the EA will always keep the best scenario.

It is important to note that a door to door (D2D) collection system should not need this type of optimization as every portal should have its own collection point.

4.3.4. Route Scheduling Optimization Module

This module will evaluate the impact of the current routes used to collect the waste and look for improvements in both the routes and vehicle schedules with respect to the criteria detailed in Table 2.

To this end, the user will need to set some input scenario from which the agents and skills will be modelled as follows:

- **Deposit Points:** Models and initial location for deposit points. The deposit points will be immovables and will be used for scheduling their collection in as many routes as needed.
- **Vehicles:** Model and main features of the vehicles available for collecting the points. The module will try to balance collection among several vehicles if needed.
- **Vehicle Drivers:** Drivers will control the vehicles travelling through the scenario using them. This will provoke the vehicles to emit gases and consume fuel for impacts calculation of the proposed schedule.
- **Transport Network:** for the citizens to find their nearest containers and make use of them will be loaded automatically to cover the study area.

The module will also use a EA strategy for making changes in a set (population) of route schedules (including the current one) and evaluate if the result provides a lower or greater impact. Each iteration the algorithm will modify the periodicity, route itineraries, driver assigned deposit points, number of vehicles or vehicles types of the element in the population of solutions. Just the same as for Section 3.3.1, the resulting scenario will be compared keeping the best scenario with respect to the previous KPIs and passing it to a new iteration.

4.3.5. Best selection of treatments

This module will select the best collection of treatments plants (including the storage of biogas) for the scenario. Aspects like the technologies, the sizing and localization of different treatments plant will be considered. The algorithm will simulate the transport of the different fractions of waste generated in the scenario to the different treatments plants and will evaluate the impact of every solution with respect to the KPIs in Table []. Every treatment plant modelled will have the following characteristics:

- **Economic costs:** including building and demolition costs, operational costs
- **RAW materials:** efficiency in recovery of secondary RAW materials
- **Environmental impacts:** the same aspects as in Section 3.3.2.
- **Social response** that of the construction or management of the treatment plant will have over the citizens.
- **Legal restrictions** with respect to distance to the population and surface requirements to be able to operate.

As before, a EA will be used to perform the optimization. In this case, the EA will first create a set of solutions that consists of:

- a selection of treatments between the pool of potential treatments between: landfill, incineration, mechanically-biological classification plant, classification plant, anaerobic digestion, composting, recycling plant for the different fractions (including nappies, R20), and valorisation of the different fractions (including R19 and R20)
- a potential localization (between a set of potential localization fixed in the scenario) and finally,
- a sizing for every treatment plan.

As before, the EA then modify this population of solutions and will run a simulation to evaluate it with respect to the previous KPIs defined. As in Section 3.3.1, the resulting scenario will be compared keeping the best scenario with respect to the previous KPIs and passing it to a new iteration.

4.3.6. Overall optimization module

All the above-mentioned modules will allow both their use independently or their combined use in a co-evolutionary algorithm. Each module's EA is executed separately sending its resultant scenario as input for the next module to optimize. Therefore, it will be possible to create multi objectives optimization scenarios (in the sense of the objects to optimize, not the objectives).

5. Green Procurement

The objective of the Green Procurement tool, further detailed in Deliverable D1.3, is to provide the user with the mechanisms to build and evaluate a public tender based on green principles. The following sections present several mock-ups of the user interface explaining the main actions that the users can perform.

5.1. Access to the Green Procurement tool

The Green Procurement tool will be accessible through the side menu of the W4T-Core (Figure 19. Access to the Green Procurement Tool.. Please note that W4T-Core has been described in Deliverable D2.1.

Figure 19. Access to the Green Procurement Tool.

On access, the user will be presented with the two main functionalities of the module:

- a) **Create new green procurement tender.** This functionality provides a wizard, a kind of helper, that lets the user create a new tender and define the parameters that are going to be evaluated to comply with the green procurement principles. Details of the options to be included can be found in Deliverable D1.3.
- b) **Monitor existing green procurement tenders.** This functionality allows to edit unpublished tenders, add new offers to published tenders, and close tenders so that the submitted offers can be evaluated.

Figure 20. Functionalities of the green Procurement Module.

5.2. Create new green procurement

When the user selects the option **Create new green procurement**, the tool will provide a form to introduce the necessary data to define the general details of the document, such as the product on which the tender is based and its period of validity (Figure 20). The specific fields for the organization details of the tenderer will be automatically retrieved and filled from the user profile. Nevertheless, these fields will be editable in case the user needs to modify them.

Figure 21. Green Procurement Questionnaire.

Once the general details have been defined, the user will then proceed to choose the specific aspects that will be evaluated in the tender (economical, environmental, social, etc.). For each type of aspect, the user will be presented with a view on which they can select the particular aspects relevant to the tender, provide a score determining the importance of the aspect within the overall evaluation, and assign threshold values to help discriminate offers based on priorities (Figure 21, Figure 22, and Figure 23).

Figure 22. Definition of the socio-economical aspects of the green procurement.

Figure 23. Definition of the social aspects of the green procurement.

Figure 24. Definition of the environmental aspects of the green procurement

After the definition and parameterization of the green procurement aspects, **all the data introduced by the user will be integrated and formatted into an editable document** that will become the final specification of the tender. The user will be able to modify the document to their liking so as to properly define and include any additional information that must be taken into consideration. The user will also be able to save the tender for later reviewing, or export the document for printing. The text shown on Figure 25 is used just as an example.

Figure 25. Final revision of the tender.

5.3. Monitor existing green procurement

When the user selects the option **Monitor a green procurement**, the tool will provide a list of all the tenders created by the user (Figure 26). At first glance, the user will be able to identify the important details about the tenders, such as the date of publication, the number of offers submitted, and the status. Specifically, the status of a tender refers to the three possible states of the tender lifecycle, as follows:

- Unpublished:** The user has already begun to elaborate a new tender, but it is not yet available to the public. Some details or aspects may or may not be fully defined. The user can modify all the data and aspects of an unpublished tender. The user can not add any offers to an unpublished tender.
- Published:** The tender is already fully defined and is available to the public. Therefore, the user cannot modify any of its details or aspects. The user will be able to review the specification and upload the new offers that match the tender requirements.
- Closed:** When the period of validity of the tender comes to an end, the tender is automatically closed. A user cannot modify the details or aspects of a closed tender, nor add additional offers.

The user can access the full details of each tender by clicking on its name to consult the complete text (Figure 26. List of green procurements.), and the aspects being evaluated (Figure 28). The modification of this information will only be possible if the tender is still in unpublished status. If a tender is already closed, the user can additionally see the offer to which the tender was awarded (Figure 27), as well as all the other offers that were submitted.

Name	Description	Start date	Status	Offers	Publish	Close
Tender1	Lorem ipsum dolor sit amet	2017-01-01	Closed	5	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
Tender2	Lorem ipsum dolor sit amet	2017-01-02	Closed	2	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
Tender3	Lorem ipsum dolor sit amet	2017-02-11	Published	1	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Tender4	Lorem ipsum dolor sit amet	2017-03-27	Published	7	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Tender5	Lorem ipsum dolor sit amet	2017-04-04	Closed	0	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
Tender9	Lorem ipsum dolor sit amet	2017-05-02	Published	0	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Tender10	Lorem ipsum dolor sit amet	2017-05-11	Closed	20	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
Tender11	Lorem ipsum dolor sit amet	2017-05-21	Closed	15	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
Tender12	Lorem ipsum dolor sit amet	2017-06-16	Unpublished	15	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Tender13	Lorem ipsum dolor sit amet	2017-06-16	Unpublished	12	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

Figure 26. List of green procurements.

Figure 27. Text of the green procurement

Figure 28. Aspects evaluated in the green procurement

A user can add offers to a published tender through the corresponding section (Figure 29). At first glance, this section provides a list of the offers that have already been submitted, detailing the name of the submitter as well as the date of submission. From this view, the user can choose to view the specific details of an offer, consult the history of offers made by a specific submitter (Figure 30), or add a new offer by filling the corresponding form with the necessary data to evaluate the aspects of the tender (Figure 31).

Figure 29. List of offers submitted to the tender.

Figure 30. History of offer submitted by a specific organization.

As mentioned before, when the period of validity of a tender comes to an end, the tender will be automatically closed. The user will then be able to access a new view that summarizes and ranks the offers submitted to the tender in terms of compliance with the aspects defined in its formulation. The user will be able to review the specific details of each offer, choose the filter for ranking, see those offers that do not meet the threshold values expected, and select the final offer to which the tender will be awarded (Figure 33).

New offer for Tender 1 Cancel Save

Name

Offerer NIF

Address

Class	Name	Points
Economical	Economical aspect 1	<input type="text"/>
Economical	Economical aspect 2	<input type="text"/>
Economical	Economical aspect 3	<input type="text"/>
Economical	Economical aspect 4	<input type="text"/>
Social	Social aspect 1	<input type="text"/>
Social	Social aspect 1	<input type="text"/>

Next

Figure 31. Add new offer to the green procurement

Tender 1 (Closed) Select and close

Total offers sumited 8

Name	Submitter	Economical	Environmental	Social	Total score	Selected
Offer1	Submitter1	100	100	100	300	<input checked="" type="radio"/>
Offer2	Submitter2	50	100	100	250	<input type="radio"/>
Offer3	Submitter3	100	50	100	250	<input type="radio"/>
Offer4	Submitter4	50	50	100	200	<input type="radio"/>
Offer5	Submitter5	25	100	25	150	<input type="radio"/>
Offer6	Submitter6	25	25	25	75	<input type="radio"/>
Offer7	Submitter7	20	20	20	60	<input type="radio"/>
Offer8	Submitter8	20	20	20	60	<input type="radio"/>

Exit

Figure 32. Rank of submitted offers to a specific green procurement.

A Web Page

← → ↻

☰

Green Procurement

- Details
- Aspects
- Offers
- Results

Tender 1 (Closed)

Selected Offer

Name	Submitter	Economical	Environmental	Social	Total score
Offer1	<input type="checkbox"/> Submitter1	100	100	100	300

Total offers sumited **8**

Name	Submitter	Economical	Environmental	Social	Total score
Offer2	<input type="checkbox"/> Submitter2	50	100	100	250
Offer3	<input type="checkbox"/> Submitter3	100	50	100	250
Offer4	<input type="checkbox"/> Submitter4	50	50	100	200
Offer5	<input type="checkbox"/> Submitter5	25	100	25	150
Offer6	<input type="checkbox"/> Submitter6	25	25	25	75
Offer7	<input type="checkbox"/> Submitter7	20	20	20	60
Offer8	<input type="checkbox"/> Submitter8	20	20	20	60

Figure 33. Selection of offer that is awarded the green procurement.

6. Zero-waste Ecosystem/Event Planner

The purpose of the Zero-Waste Ecosystem/Event Planner, further detailed in Deliverable D1.3, is to provide the user with a tool to identify what amount and type of waste is generated in a specific event or ecosystem, for example a monitored building, whether residential or commercial, and to delve into the reasons behind its generation and evaluate a set of correction actions such as the green procurement, prevention campaigns, or the measures resulting from the innovative teaching materials at schools or citizen science.

6.1. Access to the Zero-Waste Ecosystem/Event Planner Tool

The Zero-Waste Ecosystem/Event Planner Tool will be accessible through the side menu of the W4T-Core (Figure 34).

Figure 34. Access to the Zero-Waste Ecosystem/Event Planner Tool

When the user accesses the tool, they will be presented with the list of Zero-Waste dashboards they have already created. The user will be able to select any dashboard and visualize its specific details. A Zero Waste dashboard is a type of dashboard that is specially dedicated to the monitoring of both Zero-Waste Events and Zero-Waste Ecosystems. The general behaviour and functionalities of the dashboards are detailed in Deliverable D2.1.

Figure 35. Zero-Waste Ecosystem/Event dashboards.

6.2. Monitor existing Zero-Waste Ecosystem/Event dashboards

On access to this section, the user will be presented with the details of the Zero-Waste dashboards created by them. At first glance, the user will be able to see the monitoring start and end dates of the Zero-Waste dashboard (related to the start and end dates of the Zero-waste Ecosystem/Event), configure whether a dashboard should be visible in the main page of the Zero-Waste Planner Tool, or delete the dashboard.

Figure 36. Existing Zero-Waste Ecosystem/Events dashboards.

6.3. Create new Zero-waste Ecosystem/Event

When the user selects the creation of a new Zero-waste Ecosystem/Event, they will be presented with a helper that will guide them through each section (Description, Waste Management, Internal Services, Communication activities, Evaluation, etc.) of the Zero-Waste questionnaire so that they fill in the required fields according to the classification explained in Deliverable D1.3 (Figure 37 and Figure 38). Each of the sections will be accessible through a side menu, for example, in the form of tabs.

Figure 37. Questionnaire for the Zero-Waste Event (general description).

	Biowaste	Paper	Glass	Packaging	Others
Points of waste separation (wheel bins)					
Litter bins (with different fractions)					

Figure 38. Questionnaire for the Zero-Waste Event (waste management).

After answering all the questionnaire fields of each of the sections, the user will be presented with the Evaluation view (Figure 39). The Evaluation view lets the user create an automatic dashboard of the Zero-Waste Ecosystem/Event. The user will configure the dashboard by providing, if possible, information about the identifiers of the entities that can be monitored, such as the waste containers that will give service to the Zero-Waste Ecosystem/Event or the KPIs. With the defined monitored entities, the Zero-Waste Planner tool will create a dashboard, on which the user can follow the state of the Zero-Waste Ecosystem or the Zero-Waste Event.

Zero Waste

https://waste4think.eu/zerowaste/

WASTE 4think

Zero Waste

According to your inputs, you need to provide data for the monitorization, you need to provide data for the creation of the dashboard.

Containers Add

	ID	Capacity (t)	
Biowaste	WC2546	1	
Glass	WC2587	1	
Packaging	WC5897	1	

KPI Add

Caption	KPI	
Percentage improper waste	KPI126	
Amount of waste	KPI127	

Manual Input Continue

Figure 39. Questionnaire for the Zero-Waste Event (evaluation).

The final view (Figure 40) visualizes the results obtained from the evaluation of the user's answers to the questionnaire, detailing the degree of compliance of the answers to the parameters defined for the evaluation of the Zero-Waste Ecosystem/Events (see Deliverable D1.3).

Figure 40. Results of the evaluation of the Zero-Waste Ecosystem/Event.

7. Social Actions

The objective of the Social Actions tool, further detailed in Deliverables D4.1, is to provide the user with the mechanisms to build and evaluate social actions. The following sections present several mock-ups of the user interface explaining the main actions that the users can perform.

7.1. Access to the Social Actions tool

The Social Actions tool will be accessible through the side menu of the W4T-Core (Figure 41. Access to the Social Actions tool).

Figure 41. Access to the Social Actions tool.

On access to the Social Actions tool, the user will be presented with a list of the existing social strategies defined by them. This list gives a general information about each strategy and allows to **create, edit or delete** them.

Figure 42. Main view of the Social Actions tool.

7.2. Add new Strategy

When the user selects the option to **Create New Strategy** they will be presented with a guide, which will help them introduce the specific details of the new Strategy, such as the name, the description, the area of coverage, the target groups towards whom the strategy is focused, etc. (Figure 43. Form to introduce the detail the Social Strategy).

The screenshot shows a web browser window titled 'Green Procurement' with the URL 'https://waste4think.eu/greenprocurement/'. The page header features the 'WASTE 4think' logo and the title 'Social Actions'. The main content area is a form with the following fields: 'Name' (text input), 'Start' (date picker), 'End' (date picker), 'Description' (text area), 'Area' (text area), 'Target groups' (text input), 'Objective' (text input), 'Stages' (text input), and 'Cost' (text input). At the bottom of the form, there are three buttons: 'Actions', 'Prev', and 'Next'.

Figure 43. Form to introduce the detail the Social Strategy.

On access to a specific Strategy, the user will be presented with a list of the related Social Actions. This list gives a general information about each action and allows to **create, edit or delete** them (Figure 44).

The screenshot shows a web browser window titled 'W4T Rules Manager' with the URL 'https://waste4think.eu/rules/overview'. The page header features the 'WASTE 4think' logo and the title 'Social Actions'. The main content area is titled 'Promote waste separation' and includes a search bar and view mode options. The list of actions is as follows:

Action Name	Description	Delete Icon
Create New Social Action		
Distribute Flyers	Distribute flyers with about what and what not are adequate waste to organic container.	Yes
Meetings on the town hall	Meet with the citizens and promote neighbourhood actions.	Yes

At the bottom of the list, there is a pagination bar with buttons for '1', '2', '3', '4', and 'Last'.

Figure 44. Social Actions of a specific Strategy.

7.3. Add new Social Action

When the user selects the option to **Add a new Social Action** they will be presented with a guide, which will help them to introduce the specific details of the new Strategy, such as the name, the description, the period of application, the target groups towards whom the action is focused, etc. (Figure 45).

The screenshot shows a web browser window titled 'Green Procurement' with the URL 'https://waste4think.eu/greenprocurement/'. The page header features the 'WASTE 4think' logo and the title 'Social Actions'. On the left, a sidebar contains three tabs: 'Details' (selected), 'Monitoring', and 'Results'. The main content area contains the following form fields:

- Name:** A single-line text input field.
- Description:** A multi-line text area with a vertical scrollbar.
- Period:** Two date pickers labeled 'Start' and 'End', each with a calendar icon.
- Promoter:** A single-line text input field.
- Area served:** A multi-line text area with a vertical scrollbar.
- Target groups:** A single-line text input field.

A 'Next' button is located at the bottom right of the form.

Figure 45. Details of the Social Action.

Once the general details have been introduced, the user will be guided to the Monitoring view. In this view, the user will specify the KPIs that will help calculate the impact of the application of the Social Action (Figure 46).

The screenshot shows the same 'Social Actions' page, but the 'Monitoring' tab is selected in the sidebar. The form fields are:

- Objectives:** A multi-line text area with a vertical scrollbar.
- Stages:** A single-line text input field.
- Stakeholders amount:** A single-line text input field.
- Methodology:** A multi-line text area with a vertical scrollbar.

Below these fields are two sections for selecting KPIs and Targets:

- KPIs:** An 'Add' button is above a list with three items: 'Kpi_Sorting_paper_correct', 'Kpi_Sorting_paper_incorrect', and 'Kpi_Sorting_package_correct'. Each item has a 'remove' button with a trash icon.
- Target:** An 'Add' button is above a list with two items: 'waste_tipe_paper' and 'waste_type_other'. Each item has a 'remove' button with a trash icon.

'Prev' and 'Next' buttons are located at the bottom of the form.

Figure 46. Monitoring of the Social Action.

7.3. Add results to the Social Action

When the period of application of the social action finishes, the user will have to provide both quantitative and qualitative results to analyse the impact of the social action. To do so, the Social Actions module will provide with the necessary form to fill in the data (Figure 47). Please note that the specific forms that will gather the qualitative and quantitative results will vary per Strategy. Figure 47 provides just an example.

The screenshot shows a web browser window titled "Green Procurement" with the URL "https://waste4think.eu/greenprocurement/". The page header includes the "WASTE 4think" logo and the title "Social Actions". On the left, a green sidebar contains three menu items: "Details", "Monitoring", and "Results". The main content area contains the following form fields:

- Stakeholder (Real):
- Success: ★ ★ ★ ★ ☆
- Cost:
- Per citizen:
- Social Impact:
- Economical Impact:
- Lesson learned:
- Resources URL:
- Other:

At the bottom right of the form are two buttons: "Prev" and "Save".

Figure 47. Social Actions results.

8. Invoicing

The objective of the Invoicing Module, further detailed in Deliverables D2.1 and D5.1, is to provide an interface to create and estimate the results of new invoices models fed with data from the system. The invoice module will help in the creation of new invoices models that will be tested upon real and simulated data to test the viability and sustainability of the different models.

8.1. Access to the Invoicing tool

The Invoicing tool will be accessible through the side menu of the W4T-Core. Please note that W4T-Core has been described in Deliverable D2.1 (Figure 48).

Figure 48. Access to the Invoicing Module

8.2. Manage of the invoices

On access to the Invoice Module, the user will be presented with a list of the existing invoices defined by them. This list gives a general information about each invoice and allows to **create, edit or delete** them.

Figure 49. Main view of the Invoicing Module

8.3. Creation of a new invoice model

If the user selects the option to **Create a new invoicing** model, they will be presented with a helper that will guide them in this creation process. The creation process is split into three steps, each one represented by a different view. These views will be also accessible through a side menu, for example, through tabs located on the left side:

- The **Details** view allows to manage the fixed and variable cost elements that will be covered by the invoicing model (Figure 50). The user can also select the scenario on which they want to test the new model: a) *real* with the measurements being recorded directly from the pilots, b) *simulated* with any of the simulations scenarios already defined by the user. The user will also provide a relevant name for the invoicing model for future reference.
- The **Target group** view allows to define the target groups on which the new invoicing model will be tested (citizens, business, educational organizations, etc.) (Figure 51). The user will also be able to define the rules that determine the belonging of an element to a specific group. On selection of each target group, the user is presented with the set of variables relevant to that group that can then be used to build the final formula for the invoicing model.
- The **Report** view allows to test the new invoicing model. For that, the user will be presented with a special type of dashboard that will graphically present how the specific parts of the invoice model affect each target group (Figure 52). This view will also feature a control panel that will let the user adjust the formula of the invoice model in terms of the variables that are affected within each target group and type of the cost (fixed or variable), and the specific arithmetic operations to perform.

W4T Rules Manager

https://waste4think.eu/rules/overview

Invoicing

WASTE 4think

Details

Target Group

Report

Name:

Scenario: Zamudio:Real

Fixed Cost		Total	60k
Concept	Quantity		
Infraestructure	10k		
Salaries	50k		
Add New	-		

Variable cost		Total	60k
Vairable	Origin	Cost	
Bag	Manual	60k	
Add New			

Cancel Next

Figure 50. Definition of the elements of the invoice.

W4T Rules Manager

https://waste4think.eu/rules/overview

Invoicing

WASTE 4think

Details

Target Group

Report

Definition

Name	Rule	Count	Erase
Citizen	rule_is_citizen	3.000	
Business	rule_is_business	200	
Add New	-		

Variables

Name	affect	property	erase
Area	Fixed	area	
Bags	Variable	bags_produced	
Add New	-		

Cancel Report

Figure 51. Definition of the target group.

Figure 52. Dashboard of the Invoicing Module

9. References

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Comments from external reviewers

External reviewer 1

DATE: 4.12.2017

Issue	Yes	No	Score (1=low to 5=high)	Comments
Is the format of the document correct?	x		5	
Does the format of the document meet the objectives of the work done?	x		5	
Does the index of the document Collect precisely the tasks and issues that need to be reported?	x		5	
Is the content of the document clear and well described?	x		3	See the comments in text.
Does the content of each section describe the advance done during the task development?	x		4	The current status of development is not clear.
Does the content have sufficient Technical description to make clear the research and development performed?	x		4	The blind text should be replaced by real samples.
Are all the figures and tables numerated and described?	x		4	Just one is missing.
Are the indexes correct?	x		5	
Is the written English correct?	x		3	There are some screen shoots not in English.
Main technical terms are correctly referenced?		x	1	There are many missing.
Glossary present in the document?		x	1	Should be included.

Name: Andreas Schmidt

Partner: MOBA

External reviewer 2

DATE: 11.12.2017

Issue	Yes	No	Score (1=low to 5=high)	Comments
Is the format of the document correct?	x			Minor displacements in google docs. Page 21 blank? Figure on page 32 has graphic errors.
Does the format of the document meet the objectives of the work done?	x			
Does the index of the document Collect precisely the tasks and issues that need to be reported?	x			
Is the content of the document clear and well described?	x			
Does the content of each section describe the advance done during the task development?	x			No specific tasks mentioned in sections? So not sure what the advance is and can only get description.
Does the content have sufficient Technical description to make clear the research and development performed?	x			
Are all the figures and tables numerated and described?	x			
Are the indexes correct?		x		None match. Might be due to import in google docs?
Is the written English correct?	x			
Main technical terms are correctly referenced?	x			
Glossary present in the document?		x		Terminology is integrated, but might be useful to have separate glossary?

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